

THE PRINCIPAL SOURCE ROCKS FOR PETROLEUM GENERATION IN THE DAHOMEY BASIN, SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The Upper Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) Araromi Shale formation in the Nigeria sector of the Dahomey basin has been investigated for its petroleum generation potential. From three exploratory wells, Araromi, Bode Ashe and Gbekebo in the eastern end (west of Niger Delta), source rock potential has been evaluated for over one hundred (100) drill core and ditch cutting samples. The investigated shallow marine shale facies have Total Organic Carbon (TOC) value range of 0.50-4.78wt% and Hydrogen Index (HI) value range of 1-327mgHC/gTOC with the maceral composition of liptinite (av. 26.0%) and abundance of vitrinite (av. 38.1%) plus inertinite (av. 35.9%) in all the samples investigated. Vitrinite reflectance values vary from 0.51-0.68%R_o. The T_{max} values vary from 398°C-437°C and the kerogen Types include type II, II/III, III, and IV in all the samples. The Source Potential (SP) values range from 0.01-14.56kgHC/ton of rock. Biomarker analysis of the shale samples generally reveal a bimodal n-alkane envelope with maxima between (nC₁₆ and nC₁₈) and (nC₂₇ and nC₂₉) suggesting that the source organic matter were derived from a variable mixture of algae and higher plant materials with q relative higher input from marine algae as reveal by the presence of the C₃₀ 24-n-propyl cholestane (%C₃₀ sterane range from 0.45 to as high as 5.23%). The presence of organic matter of marine algae (%C₂₇ sterane av. 52% and positive detection of C₃₀ sedimentary n-propyl cholestane av. 3.7%) suggest that the control on the HI as an indication of source rock quality in varying level of organic matter preservation. The source rocks have predominantly gas prone with lesser oil prone organic matter ranging from immature to marginally mature at shallow levels but reaching proven mature levels in the subsurface. Hydrocarbons in the basin would be predominantly gas dominated, generated from deeper Cretaceous source rock (marine shale) in the subsurface levels with greater chances of heavy oils and tars at shallow levels.

KEYWORDS: Upper Cretaceous, Hydrogen Index, sedimentary rock, petroleum generation

INTRODUCTION

The search for hydrocarbons in the Cretaceous source rocks in the Nigerian in land sedimentary basins has been a major task for many decades now. The efforts were to bust the oil and gas exploration and production activities and also adequately tap the natural resources in the country. Geoscience research in the aspects of hydrocarbon search in the Nigeria sector of the Dahomey basin has been so few for many years. In the last decade, there have been considerable interest and geosciences researches in the aspects of hydrocarbon search in the basin. Recent exploration and prospect re-evaluation efforts in the Nigeria segment of the basin have been encouraged following oil discovery and production in the neighboring Benin republic sector west of the basin and the social unrest in the prolific Niger Delta, east of the basin.

The Dahomey basin is an extensive sedimentary basin in the Gulf of Guinea. It extends from southeastern Ghana through Togo and Benin Republic on the west side to the Okitipupa ridge/Benin Hinge line on the west of Niger Delta. Shale samples (drill cores and ditch cuttings) for this study came from the Araromi and Gbekebo wells drilled in the eastern part of the Dahomey basin, southwestern Nigeria (Fig. 1). The drill core samples were collected from Geological Survey of Nigeria Agency (GSNA), Kaduna main office. This work is to contribute to the geosciences research and data generation activity by assessing and documenting the organic geochemical parameters and hydrocarbon generation potential of the Araromi shales in the Nigeria sector of the Dahomey basin. This paper will also throw more light on the possibility of Cretaceous sourced oil in the overlying prolific Tertiary Niger Delta which is at the eastern side of the basin.

Geological setting

The break-up of the Gondwanaland as a result of “continental drift” led to the subsequent opening of the South Atlantic Ocean during the Mesozoic Era (Stoney, 1995; Mpanda, 1997). This event is also connected to the evolution of the Dahomey Basin. Several hypotheses have been developed as to the origin and evolution of the basin. The rift hypothesis is widely supported, on the basis of several salient features characterising the basin.

During the rifting stage in the Lower Jurassic – Early Cretaceous, there was basement fracturing and initial separation between the African and South American plates. At this time, several marginal basins developed consequent to block faulting, fragmentation and subsidence on the central Paleozoic basement rock (Asmus and Ponte, 1973; Ojeda, 1982; Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981). The early movements were in the Early Cretaceous when there was transcurrent movements on the oceanic fracture systems especially the Romanche, Chain and Charcot fractures during the drifting stages of separation of South America from Africa in the Campanian to Tertiary times. Consequent to the opening of the South Atlantic Ocean, there was landward extensional and transtensional movement (drift stage) during the Upper Cretaceous to Tertiary. Horizontal movements along the oceanic fracture zones were translated to vertical movements leading to block faulting and subsequent development of horsts and grabens (Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981).

Adediran and Adegoke, 1987 proposed a four stage evolutionary model for the Gulf of Guinea basin (Dahomey Basin inclusive); as follows:

Stage 1 – The deposition of thick clastic sediments mostly immature sandstones and fresh water shales in the intracratonic basin.

Stage 2 – Reworked sands and silts intercalated with shales of fluvial – lacustrine origin deposited within the grabens during a period of tectonic activity, erosion and sedimentation.

Stage 3 – Paralic sequence (in the northern basins) and evaporitic deposits (in the southern basins) marking the beginning of marine incursion into the basin after the separation of South America from Africa.

Stage 4 – Marine sediments rich in fauna and flora marking the final stage of the development of the Gulf of Guinea basins.

The stratigraphic setting of the Dahomey Basin has been described in detail in the works of Adegoke, 1969; Ogbe, 1970; Kogbe, 1974; Billman, 1976; Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981; Ako et al., 1980; Okosun, 1990; Adekeye, 2005 and Adekeye et al., 2006. These authors reported five lithostratigraphic formations covering the Cretaceous to Tertiary ages. The formations from the oldest to the youngest include: Abeokuta Group comprises of Ise, Afowo and Araromi formations (Cretaceous), Ewekoro Formation (Paleocene), Akinbo Formation (Late Paleocene-Early Eocene), Oshosun Formation (Eocene) and Ilaro Formation (Eocene) Fig.2. Substantial amount of sediments were deposited in fault-controlled depressions in the Dahomey Basin during the Late Cretaceous. Post Santonian marine transgression accompanied the subsidence and drowning of continental margins, which brought about the deposition of very thick sequence of continental grits and pebbly sands over the entire basin (Lehner and Ruiters, 1977). In some places, mudstones and shales with thin limestone beds were formed. This lithostratigraphic formation is referred to as Abeokuta Group comprising Ise, Afowo and Araromi formations (Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981). A continuation of the marine transgression during the Paleocene led to the deposition of shallow marine limestones of the Ewekoro Formation and the shales of the Akinbo Formation (Ogbe, 1970; Okosun, 1990). On top of the Paleocene sequence is the Eocene shales of the Oshosun Formation and the sandstones of the Ilaro Formation (Okosun, 1990; Idowu et al., 1993).

Sample Material and Laboratory Analyses

A. Hydrocarbon Source Rock Potential

Representative core samples of the Late Cretaceous Araromi Formation in the Dahomey Basin, SW Nigeria were collected from the Araromi and Gbekebo wells (Fig. 1) drilled on the eastern margin of the basin where it shares a border with the western Niger Delta. The samples were analysed for their total organic carbon content (TOC) and hydrocarbon source quality by Rock-Eval Pyrolysis using standard experimental techniques. Bitumen extracts from selected organic rich source rock samples were analysed for their biomarker and stable carbon isotope composition of *n*-alkanes using the GC, GC-MS and GC-MS-MS techniques described below.

Selected shale samples were crushed to less than 2mm and impregnated in epoxy for qualitative reflected light microscopy. Where organic constituents are sparse, kerogen concentrates were prepared, mounted and polished. Organic petrology studies were carried out on a Reichert Jung Polyvar Photomicroscope equipped with halogen and HBO lamp, a photomultiplier and computer unit at the Zentraleinrichtung für Elektronenmikroskopie (ZELMI), Technische Universität Berlin, Germany. Mean random reflectance of vitrinite in oil ($R_o\%$, cf. Bustin et al., 1983) was calculated from the reflectance of at least 30 grains of vitrinite measured in random orientation using monochromatic (546nm) non-polarised light in conjunction with a x40 oil immersion objective. Calibration of the microscope photometer was achieved using standards of known reflectance (1.23 and 3.16%). Measured R_{om} values of reflectance standards confirmed the photomultiplier to be consistently linear within the range of the measurements. Data collection and evaluation were done using the coal programme by Reichert Jung and macerals were identified through the use of white light and blue light excitation at 546 and 460nm respectively. The mean reflectance as compared to the median or modal reflectance appear to be an adequate measure of thermal maturity in this study (Tissot and Welte, 1984; Pollastro and Barker, 1986).

The rock Eval pyrolysis was carried out at the Organic Geochemistry Laboratory of the Department of Mineralogy, Geochemistry and Petrology, University of Szeged, Hungary following the standard procedure of Rock Eval pyrolysis experimentation on Rock Eval II machine. The Rock-Eval II pyroanalysis has the ability of measuring the total organic carbon (TOC) content on the pulverized samples at elevated temperatures of ca. 600°C (Espitalie et al., 1977). Pyrolysis of 10-40mg of samples at 300°C for 4mins was followed by programmed pyrolysis at 25°C/min to 550°C in an atmosphere of helium.

B. Biomarker

Gas chromatography was performed on the saturated hydrocarbon fractions in order to obtain *n*-alkane and isoprenoid data as well as to determine sample concentration and complexity before GC-MS and gas chromatography-isotope ratio mass spectrometry (GC-IRMS) analyses. An HP 5890 series II gas chromatograph equipped with an HP-5 coated capillary column (60m x 0.25mm, 0.25µm film thickness) was used. The GC oven was initially set at 50°C for 2 min. and then the temperature was ramped from 50°C at 4°C/min to 300°C and held at final temperature for 20 minutes with hydrogen as the carrier gas (flow rate approx 2ml/min and initial pressure of 100kPa).

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry-mass spectrometry (GC-MS-MS) analyses of saturated hydrocarbon fractions were performed on a Varian CP3800 GC split/splitless injector (280°C) linked to a Varian 1200 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (electron voltage 70eV, filament current 50µA, source temperature 230°C, quad temperature 40°C, multiplier voltage 1400V, interface temperature 300°C). After addition of 5β-cholane internal standard, the samples were analysed in scan mode (50-550 amu/sec) or selected ion monitoring mode (SIM) for 30 ions (dwell 35ms per ion) or in MS-MS mode where up to 8 parent/daughter transitions could be monitored, using argon as the collision gas at a pressure of 2mTorr and with a collision energy of -10eV. The sample (1µl) in dichloromethane was injected by a Varian CP8400 autosampler and the split opened after 1 minute. Separation was performed on a fused silica capillary column (60m x 0.32mm i.d) coated with 0.25µm methylsilicone (HP-1). The GC was temperature programmed over 3 ramps from 4°C-300°C (40°C-75°C at 10°C/min, held for 1min at 175°C, followed by 175°C-225°C at 6°C/min and held for 1 min at 225°C, and 225-300 at 4°C/min) and was held at final temperature for 20 minutes with helium as the carrier gas (flow approx 1ml/min, initial pressure of 30kPa, split at 30 ml/min).

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Organic Matter Richness

The quantity of organic matter (OM) in a rock is a direct measure of the Total Organic Carbon content (TOC). The analysed Araromi shale samples have a value range of 0.5-4.78wt% (Tables 1 and 2), which indicates variable source rock organic carbon quality from poor to excellent. There is an overall trend of increasing TOC values down the well (Fig. 3) suggesting better source rock quality in deeply buried intervals. Most of the samples have TOC >0.5wt% which is the minimum threshold value for hydrocarbon generation in siliciclastic source rock (Tissot and Welte, 1978, Hedberg et al., 1979). The TOC values suggest that Araromi shales have adequate organic matter constituents for hydrocarbon generation.

Hydrogen Index (HI)

The hydrogen index (HI) values vary from 1-327mgHC/gTOC (Tables 1 and 2) thus, suggesting source rock quality that spans from non-source potential through to gas/oil and oil generating potentials. In general, the OM is considered to be a mixture of Type II and Type III and a downhole profile of increasing HI concomitant with the TOC trend is apparent in the well logs. Deeper sections of the formation seem to be more organic rich and thus presumably have greater potential to generate liquid hydrocarbon. Additionally as shown in Fig. 3, two organic rich intervals (A and B) are obvious from the geochemical log and some core samples within the interval B contain HI values as high as 327mgHC/gTOC suggesting that more organic rich sections in the deep offshore equivalent of the strata may have greater potential to generate liquid petroleum.

Samples with HI value range of 1-45mgHC/gTOC having kerogen Type IV indicate a highly reworked terrestrially derived OM perhaps in a highly oxic depositional environment. They form inert source which have no potential for hydrocarbon generation. The samples with HI values of 45-132mgHC/gTOC with kerogen Type III suggest woody or herbaceous organic matter origin having gas prone characteristics. Those samples with in the range of 151-327mgHC/gTOC consisting of kerogen Type II and Type II/III usually at the basal part of the wells contain oil and mixture of oil and gas prone kerogens.

Thermal Maturation

The thermal maturation (T_{max}) measured from the Rock Eval pyrolysis varies from 398°C to 437°C while the vitrinite reflectance values vary from 0.50 to 0.68% R_o . These values suggest that the source rocks are thermally immature to marginally mature for hydrocarbon generation. The plots of Rock Eval T_{max} against hydrogen index also show thermally immature to early mature source rocks with respect to hydrocarbon generation and dominance of a mixture of oil prone Type II and gas prone Type III kerogens (Fig. 4).

Source Potential

The source potential (SP) values vary from 0.01-14.56kgHC/ton of rock (Tables 1 and 2). The SP values are generally lower than the 2kgHC/ton of rock expected for good source rock (Dymann et al., 1996), suggesting little or no oil source rock potential but some potential for gas. Samples with higher SP values ranging from 3.01kgHC/ton of rock to 12.88kgHC/ton of rock suggest a moderate source rock with fair oil potential.

Maceral Analysis

The organic petrological study of the disseminated organic matter in the shale samples was carried out using the techniques in studying optical characteristics of finely dispersed organic matter particles in coals, coaly shales and carbonaceous shales. Terminologies of Stach et al., 1982 modified in Teichmuller, 1987 were used here. Selected shale samples were polished and observed under organic petrological microscope. The different macerals of vitrinite, liptinite and inertinite were observed. Photomicrographs of representative macerals are shown in Fig. 5. In general, the maceral composition include liptinite (av. 26.0%), vitrinite (av. 38.1%) and inertinite (av. 35.9%) in all the samples investigated. The dominance of vitrinite and inertinite macerals suggests terrestrially derived, reworked and oxidized organic matter in the shale sediments. There is no particular maceral variation pattern or zonation down deep in all the wells.

Biomarker compositions of the shales

Core samples analysed by Gas Chromatography (GC) display a bimodal *n*-alkane GC fingerprint envelope with maxima between $nC_{16} - nC_{18}$ and $nC_{27} - nC_{29}$ (Fig. 6), suggesting variable inputs from both terrigenous and non-terrigenous (probably marine algal) organic matter. However, some samples display a unimodal *n*-alkane GC fingerprint typical of dominantly normal marine algal contribution (maximizing between nC_{16} and nC_{18}). There is a relatively high input from alga-bacterial precursors indicated by the abundance of the low molecular weight relative to high molecular weight *n*-alkane derived from terrigenous higher plants (Bray and Evans, 1961). Additionally *pr/ph* ratios vary from 0.78-2.02 reflecting anoxic to sub-oxic source rock depositional environment (Didyk et al., 1978, Volkman and Maxwell, 1986).

Steranes in the saturated hydrocarbon fractions of the bitumen extracts of the Araromi shale samples analysed by GC-MS and GC-MS-MS show the C_{27} - C_{29} distributions to be nearing a ratio of 1.1:0.9:1.0, with higher C_{27} and C_{28} compounds on occasions relative to the C_{29} sterane homologues for the $5\alpha(H), 14\alpha(H), 17\alpha(H)$ 20R configuration isomers. Figs. 7 and 8 show the sterane distributions of the bitumen extracts from the Araromi shales. The above observation suggests a relatively higher input from the marine red algae and a low level of land plant contribution to the source organic matter (Goodwin, 1973). Additionally, the presence of the C_{30} 24-*n*-propyl cholestane (detected by GC-MS-MS *m/z* 414-217 parent to daughter ion transition), confirms the relatively high marine algal contribution to the organic matter in the Araromi shales, as values of % C_{30} sterane range from 0.45 to as high as 5.23%, even in oleanane rich intervals in "Zone B" (Figure 3).

CONCLUSION

Rock Eval pyrolysis data from this study suggest that the organic rich core samples of Late Cretaceous Araromi Formation in the Dahomey Basin, southwestern Nigeria contain predominantly gas prone with lesser oil prone organic constituents ranging from immature to marginally mature at shallow levels but reaching proven maturity in the subsurface. Hydrocarbons in the basin will be predominantly gas dominated generated from deeper Cretaceous source rock in the subsurface levels with greater chances of heavy oils and tars at shallow levels.

Gas chromatographic analyses of the bitumen extract show bimodal and unimodal *n*-alkane distributions, suggesting elevated contributions of marine relative to terrigenous higher plant matter to the source organic matter. The source rock organic matter accumulations probably occurred under anoxic to sub-oxic conditions (*pr/ph* ratios range from 0.78-2.02). Sterane distributions in the shale extracts are dominated by C_{27} relative to C_{28} and C_{29} carbon homologues and the presence of significant C_{30} 24-*n*-propyl cholestane concentrations are both diagnostic of marine algal inputs. These biomarker characteristics are comparable with the deepwater oil. Araromi bitumen extracts have nearly flat *n*-alkane CSIA stable carbon isotopic profiles that suggest derivation from organic carbon from a uniform $\delta^{13}C$ composition marine algal source.

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Figure 1

Fig. 1: Map showing the sedimentary basins of Nigeria. The arrow points to the location of the Dahomey Basin on the western margin of the Niger Delta. The map to the right is an enlarged outline geological map of Dahomey basin showing the location of the Araromi and Gbekebo wells (red ring) on the eastern margin of Dahomey (west of the Niger Delta). Map modified after Adekeye et al. (2006).

AGE		FORMATION		LITHOLOGY	
		Ako et al., 1980	Omatsola and Adegoke, 1981		
TERTIARY	EOCENE	ILARO FM	ILARO FM	SANDSTONE	
		OSHOSUN FM AKINBO FM	OSHOSUN FM AKINBO FM	SILALE	
	PALEOCENE	EWEKORO FM	EWEKORO FM	LIMESTONE	
CRETACEOUS	MAASTRICHTIAN	ABEOKUTA FM	ABEOKUTAGROUP	ARAROMI FM	SHALE
	TURONIAN			AFOWO FM	SANDSTONE AND SHALE
	BARREMIAN			ISE FM	SANDSTONE

Fig. 2: Generalised stratigraphic setting of the Dahomey Basin in the southwestern Nigeria (modified and redrawn from Idowu et al., 1993)

Figure 3: Geochemical log of the Gbekebo well. Two organic rich intervals are apparent (A and B). Only one sample within the interval A contains oleanane whereas most samples in the interval B contain oleanane, with oleanane index values as high as 0.21, despite the high marine algal biomarker composition of interval B.

Figure 4: Plot of Rock-Eval HI against Tmax indicating the kerogen types and their respective hydrocarbon potentials in the analysed Araromi Formation sediments. Overlay field after Integrated Geochemical Interpretations Ltd P: IGI 2.7 geochemical interpretation software.

Figure 5: Photomicrographs of the macerals observed in the shale samples from the Araromi Formation in the Araromi borehole.

Caption to figures

1. A large huminite grain within mineral matter matrix normal white light observation, sample number Ar-140; Araromi borehole; bar scale 50µm.
2. Same field of observation as in 1, now in blue light excitation showing threads of sporinites and resinates with yellowish fluorescence intensity, sandwiched within the huminite cell structure; bar scale 50µm.
3. Discrete euhedral to subhedral grains of pyrite distributed within mineral matter and clouds of amorphous organic matter: normal white observation; sample number Ar-145; Araromi borehole; bar scale 50µm.
4. Same field of observation as in 3 now during blue light excitation; showing thin walled sporinite with yellow fluorescence in the clouds of organic matter and the non-fluorescing pyrite grains in black colour; bar scale 50µm.
5. Irregular grains of huminite within mineral matter matrix; normal white observation; sample number Ar-146; Araromi borehole; bar scale 50µm.
6. Same field of observation as in 5 now during blue light excitation showing non-fluorescing huminites in black colour associated with threads of sporinite in the lower bottom and yellowish fluorescing pollen grain ? in the upper sector of the huminite grain; bar scale 50µm.

GC mass chromatogram of Sample Ar-149

Figure 7: Figure 9. Gas chromatograms of representative saturated hydrocarbon fractions of the Araromi shale (samples GB314 and GB 307) extracts showing how *n*-alkane and isoprenoid distributions in the Araromi shale.

m/z 217 mass chromatograms

Figure 8: m/z 217 mass chromatograms showing the distribution of C₂₇-C₂₉ steranes in representative intervals within the Araromi. Note the downhole variation in the sterane distributions within the Araromi shale extracts.

Table 1: Rock Eval pyrolysis data of the Araromi (Maastrichtian) and Imo (Paleocene) formations in the Araromi borehole.

Sample Number	Depth (m)	Location	Formation	S1(mgH C/g rock)	S2 (mg HC/g rock)	SP (kg/t)	T _{max}	PI	%R _o	TOC wt%	HI(mgHC /g rock)	Kerogen Type
Ar-46	256.03	Araromi BH	Imo Shale	0.19	0.44	0.63	417	0.31	-	0.75	58	III
Ar-53	277.37	Araromi BH	Imo Shale	0.16	0.38	0.54	399	0.30	0.45	0.63	60	III
Ar-60	298.70	Araromi BH	Imo Shale	0.09	0.09	0.18	427	0.50	0.64	0.39	23	n.d
Ar-68	329.18	Araromi BH	Imo Shale	0.07	0.09	0.16	391	0.44	-	0.34	26	n.d
Ar-74	350.52	Araromi BH	Imo Shale	0.09	0.13	0.22	399	0.41	0.55	0.50	26	IV
Ar-81	371.86	Araromi BH	Imo Shale	0.09	0.35	0.44	420	0.20	0.55	0.58	60	III
Ar-88	393.19	Araromi BH	Imo Shale	0.08	0.31	0.39	419	0.21	-	0.74	41	IV
Ar-91	405.38	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.02	0.01	0.03	403	1.00	0.51	0.65	1	IV
Ar-97	435.86	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.05	0.10	0.15	419	0.36	-	0.61	16	IV
Ar-100	454.46	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.05	0.10	0.15	412	0.36	-	0.75	13	IV
Ar-105	463.29	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.04	0.05	0.09	410	0.50	-	0.66	7	IV
Ar-110	475.49	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.17	0.95	1.12	424	0.15	-	1.69	56	III
Ar-114	487.68	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.11	0.57	0.68	428	0.16	-	1.05	54	III
Ar-119	495.30	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.15	0.75	0.87	422	0.17	-	1.77	40	IV
Ar-124	505.36	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.18	0.54	0.72	420	0.25	-	1.19	45	III
Ar-132	518.16	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.08	0.26	0.34	409	0.24	-	1.02	25	IV
Ar-139	539.49	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.08	0.18	0.26	411	0.31	0.51	1.01	17	IV
Ar-145	557.78	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.21	3.10	3.31	423	0.06	0.66	2.05	151	II-III
Ar-148	566.93	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.28	5.18	5.46	424	0.05	-	2.75	188	II-III
Ar-151	572.72	Araromi BH	Araromi FM	0.52	3.70	4.22	426	0.12	-	1.83	202	II-III

Table 2. Bulk geochemical and selected biomarker parameters for the analysed Araromi shale from Gbekebo well in Dahomey Basin

Sample Number	Depth (ft)	TOC (wt%)	S1	S2	T _{max} (°C)	HI	PI	Pr/Ph	%C27	%C28	%C29	%C30	OL	C29S/S+R
GB 304	2735.7	0.50	0.00	0.01	430.00	2.00	0.00							
GB 305	2739	0.63	0.12	0.36	425.00	57.14	0.25							
GB 306	2758.8	1.02	0.14	0.51	425.00	50.00	0.22							
GB 307	2772	1.01	0.13	0.48	432.00	47.52	0.21	1.06	36.94	25.55	37.06	0.45	0.00	0.23
GB 309	2788.5	0.69	0.05	0.24	425.00	34.78	0.17							
GB 310	2798.4	0.91	0.04	0.34	430.00	37.36	0.11	1.28	45.28	26.62	28.09	0.00	0.00	0.18
GB 311	2801.7	0.99	0.06	0.55	430.00	55.56	0.10							
GB 312	2818.2	0.95	0.08	0.41	425.00	43.16	0.16							
GB 313	2824.8	1.00	0.28	0.42	432.00	42.00	0.40							
GB 314	2828.1	0.68	0.12	0.44	435.00	64.71	0.21	0.78	24.10	41.81	32.77	1.32	0.00	0.25
GB 315	2831.4	0.91	0.07	0.36	435.00	39.56	0.16	0.93	23.62	35.50	38.88	2.00	0.06	0.31
GB 316	2834.7	0.76	0.06	0.21	437.00	27.63	0.22							
GB 318	2838	0.82	0.06	0.30	431.00	36.59	0.17	1.18	22.16	39.74	36.59	1.51	0.00	0.26
GB 320	2867.7	1.24	0.06	0.15	422.00	12.10	0.29							
GB 323	2897.4	1.67	0.12	1.29	435.00	77.25	0.09							
GB 324	2904	1.70	0.06	0.83	432.00	48.82	0.07	1.25	31.95	41.15	24.29	2.61	0.00	0.31
GB 325	2910.6	1.87	0.27	3.01	427.00	160.96	0.08							
GB 326	2917.2	2.13	0.18	5.25	430.00	246.48	0.03		38.20	38.47	20.83	2.50	0.00	0.26
GB 327	2920.5	2.12	0.17	3.01	427.00	141.98	0.05							
GB 402	2963.4	1.97	0.21	1.39	432.00	70.56	0.13		31.39	31.00	33.51	4.11		0.23
GB 421	3144.9	1.66	0.28	0.42	415.00	25.30	0.40							
GB 450	3319.8	2.24	0.31	5.01	433.00	223.66	0.06	1.13	33.68	38.20	25.09	3.02	0.20	0.29
GB 451	3323.1	2.52	0.32	6.44	432.00	255.56	0.05							
GB 454	3333	4.78	0.81	13.75	434.00	287.66	0.06							
GB 455	3336.3	3.33	0.73	10.30	431.00	309.31	0.07	2.02	30.15	30.74	33.89	5.23	0.21	0.16
GB 456	3342.9	3.94	1.29	12.88	426.00	327.07	0.09	1.39	37.91	33.23	26.73	2.13	0.12	0.47
GB 460	3372.6	1.54	0.31	1.09	434.00	70.78	0.22	0.96	34.20	33.56	29.00	3.24	0.09	0.19

HI = Hydrogen index (100*S2/TOC). PI = production Index S1/(S1+S2). Pr/Ph = pristane/phytane. % C27-C30 = % individual C27-C30 $\alpha\alpha\alpha$ sterane to sum of C27-29 $\alpha\alpha\alpha$ regular steranes. OL = 18 α (H) + 18 β (H) oleanane/C₃₀ 17 α (H),21 β (H)- Hopane. C29 S/S+R = ratio of 5 α (H),14 α (H),21 α (H) - steranes (20S/S+R) thermal maturity parameter.

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